

Amendments to Jungian Function Positions

Nathan Robert Rassi

In Dr. John Beebe's work, *Energies and Patterns in Psychological Type* (2017), Dr. Beebe suggests that the opposing function exists in opposition to the hero function. However, this paper introduces the concept of *unconscious reflection*. The concept of unconscious reflection suggests that the shadow functions do not oppose the conscious functions, but that they exist in conjunction with the conscious functions. This is illustrated in accordance with the following amendments to Jungian theory.

Fe nemesis: worried about mistreatment, in relation to Fi hero.

Te nemesis: worried that there are not enough facts to form a conclusion, in relation to Ti hero (Rassi, 2025); bothered by a lack of being informed; favors information from others.

Fe critic: critical of lacking kindness.

Te critic: critical of whether or not there is enough material or physical evidence; critical of a lack of being informed; favors information from others.

In all cases, it can be observed that the shadow functions do not exist to oppose the conscious functions, nor are they a negative projection of the conscious functions. Rather, the shadow functions largely exist to fulfill the interests of the conscious functions.

References

Beebe, J. (2017). *Energies and Patterns in Psychological Type: The reservoir of consciousness* [E-book edition]. Routledge.

Rassi, N. R. (2025). *Cognitive Functions Modelling and Analysis*.
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